

science and policy
for a healthy future

Generating indicators incorporating HBM-GV – first visualisation examples

Additional Deliverable Report

AD5.5

WP5 - Translation of results into policy

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2 Glossary

BBzP - Benzyl butyl phthalate

CI - Confidence Interval

DEHP - Di-2-ethylhexyl phthalate

DEP - Diethyl phthalate

DiBP - Diisobutyl phthalate

DiNP - Diisononyl phthalate

DnBP - Di-n-butyl phthalate

EEA - European Environment Agency

EFSA - European Food Safety Authority

HBM - Human Biomonitoring

HBM4EU - Human Biomonitoring Initiative in Europe

HBM-GV - Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values

IPCHEM - Information Platform for Chemical Monitoring

ISCED - International Standard Classification of Education

PFHxS - Perfluoro-1-hexanesulfonate

PFNA - Perfluoro-n-nonanoic acid

PFOA - perfluorooctanoic acid

PFOS - perfluorooctane sulfonate

SVHC - Substance of very high concern

TWI - Tolerable Weekly Intake

UBA - German Environment Agency (Umweltbundesamt)

VITO - Flemish Institute for Technological Research (Vlaamse Instelling voor Technologisch Onderzoek)

WP - Work package

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3 Abstract/Summary

Under the Human Biomonitoring Initiative in Europe (HBM4EU), human biomonitoring (HBM) based indicators are being developed that can help answer relevant policy questions focusing on chemical exposure. These policy questions are addressed in the [scoping documents](#) for each prioritised substance/substance group within the project. HBM based indicators may help to illustrate research results in an easy interpretable way.

As there is still a limited number of datasets in the HBM4EU repository for each substance/substance group for phthalates, bisphenol A (BPA), per- and polyfluorinated compounds (PFAS), aprotic solvents and cadmium (Cd), this deliverable is making first examples of visualisation with our indicators. In this context, quality aspects have been discussed in the last deliverable AD5.3. The examples illustrate the use of the indicators to answer policy questions for future use. Following on that additional deliverable, with the aggregated data currently available in the HBM4EU repository, the aim of this additional deliverable is to harvest and construct indicators with the available aggregated data to:

1. Summarise exposure levels per country
2. Identify of most exposed sub-groups using stratifiers such as: gender, age, socio-economic status (SES), country, year (time trends and monitor differences after enforcement of new legislation).

For this purpose, two different types of HBM-based indicators are going to be visualised:

- a) Result indicators that will present time and spatial trends of HBM exposure data. Quantitative and qualitative analysis will allow an evaluation on policy effectiveness
- b) Impact indicators that place HBM data in a health risk context by including the respective HBM guidance values (HBM-GVs)

To link the work on HBM-GV with indicators is necessary when generating impact indicators for assessing health impacts. Therefore, a close exchange between T5.2 (Development and consolidation of HBM guidance values (HBM-GVs)) and T5.4 (HBM-based indicators) is necessary.

This Additional Deliverable is trying to create first examples on how the HBM-based indicators may look like with the data that is available from the HBM4EU repository (status: July 2020). As there are still difficulties in harmonisation of datasets within the repository it was decided to mainly base the derivation of indicators on the DEMOCOPHES data and any other dataset that has become available and uploaded in the HBM4EU repository.

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4 Introduction

Indicators are illustrators of data that bring information in an easy and accessible way to a broader audience be it scientists, policy makers or the general population.

Under Task 5.4, a framework was developed to apply HBM-based indicators and how they can contribute to answer the policy questions derived in the Scoping Documents for each prioritised substance/substance group under HBM4EU.

As mentioned in our previous deliverable, [AD5.3 “Case-study report on HBM-indicators”](#), these are designed to **answer key policy questions and support chemical policy making by using HBM data collections**. The indicators will include aspects such as policy monitoring, time and spatial trends in internal exposure, internal exposure of vulnerable groups and specific subpopulations.

According to the strategy and concept that was developed in the first year of the project ([Deliverable 5.3](#), Buekers et al., 2018), the HBM4EU WP5 indicators are classified as follows:

- Result indicators
- Impact indicators

Measurement of the **concentration of a substance in blood or urine could be defined as ‘HBM indicator of internal exposure’** and is an example of a **result indicator**. It does not give information on the hazard of the chemical, at which level an effect will occur (potency) or of the risk of being exposed. Furthermore, **HBM data can be compared with a level below which no adverse health effects are expected (for example, the HBM guidance value or HBM-GV)**. In this case, **impact indicators** can be developed.

The previous deliverable described how to display and frame these indicators, as well as the quality aspects that are needed for the comparison of datasets.

In this deliverable, we will develop indicators and compare them to the HBM-GV_{GenPop} available for **phthalates (DEHP, as a first example), BPA, aprotic solvents, cadmium (Cd) and PFAS (PFHxS, PFNA, PFOA and PFOS)**.

The available data was the one provided by the countries as the data from the aligned studies is not available yet. The aligned studies are the product of an extensive EU wide collection of harmonised HBM data under WP8. The purpose of which is to obtain samples and HBM data across Europe by harmonising ongoing HBM studies in 21 countries¹.

This document focuses only on five substance groups: phthalates, BPA, PFAS, aprotic solvents and cadmium, showing the availability of HBM data from the repository and finally make a first visualisation of the indicators showing their potential of interpreting data and answering policy questions.

Indicators developed are based on the aggregated data in the repository of HBM4EU, therefore permission was sought and granted from the Data Controller or the Data Owner/Data Provider.

We highlighted in our last Deliverable that robust and scientifically proven answers to the policy questions can only be produced when they are based on harmonised and quality assured data which will become available with the aligned studies. But for having first examples how the

¹ Within the aligned studies, 3 age groups of interest are investigated: children age 6-11, teenagers age 12-19 and adults 20-39 years of age. Within each age group, 10 to 11 different countries will participate. The spread of these countries over the 4 geographical regions of Europe (N, E, S, W) is in proportion to the percentage of inhabitants of those regions. Each country provides 300 samples, with the exception of a few smaller countries who are providing a reduced number of samples. In each age group, exposure to different priority chemicals are analysed. In children: phthalates and DINCH, and flame retardants; in teenagers: phthalates and DINCH, and perfluorinated compounds; and in adults: cadmium, bisphenols and PAHs.

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indicators may look like and how they can be used for data interpretation, this additional deliverable 5.5 is creating for the first-time representative indicators from the repository data for each of the substances or substance group.

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5 HBM-based indicators - overview

Based on the [Deliverable 5.3](#) and the conceptual framework derived for developing HBM-based indicators, the indicators chosen were:

- Temporal increase or stabilisation of internal exposure possibly related to policy action (result indicator)
- Possible effectiveness of policy actions in minimising chemical exposure. E.g. Efficiency indicators (Type C): Are we improving? Policy effectiveness indicators (Type D): Are the measures working? (result indicator)
- Inequality of internal chemical exposure (result indicator)
- Health relevance regarding internal chemical exposure (impact indicator)

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6 HBM-based indicators for phthalate exposure

In a first step for the derivation of indicators the availability of datasets on phthalates within the HBM4EU repository was checked. In a next step, indicators for one representative phthalate DEHP were derived to show the potential for data interpretation and policy advice.

6.1 Overview of phthalate data in the HBM4EU repository (status: July 2020)

The following table (Table 1) gives an overview of the data that are available in the HBM4EU repository on the phthalates DEHP (Di-2-ethylhexyl phthalate, CAS 117-81-7), BBzP (Benzyl butyl phthalate, CAS 85-68-7), DiBP (Diisobutyl phthalate, CAS 84-69-5), DnBP (Di-n-butyl phthalate, CAS 84-74-2), DiNP (Diiso nonyl phthalate, CAS 28553-12-0) and DEP (Diethyl phthalate, CAS 84-66-2).

The data available in the repository comprises HBM studies from the years 2006-2017. From the selected phthalates there are in total 21 datasets from 13 different countries available. The dominating matrix is morning urine, but also datasets with spot urine samples exist. Stratification for different age groups is possible for children (3-5 years; 6-11 years), teenagers (12-19 years) and adults (20-39 years; 40-59 years). Some studies have also the possibility to stratify for sex and socioeconomic status.

Table 1: Overview of datasets from selected phthalates (their metabolites relevant for HBM-GVs) in HBM4EU repository (status: July 2020)

Phthalate	Country	Study	Sampling years	Matrix	Stratification
DEHP (OH-MEHP and oxo-MEHP)	Austria	EAA_IC-HBM_integration IPCHEM (Human biomonitoring of industrial chemicals)	2009	Morning urine	Mother (28+ y) and child (6-11 y) pairs
	Czech Republic	Czech HBM Children's exposure (HBM-CE)	2016-2017	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
		DEMOCOPHES	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
	Denmark	Copenhagen Puberty Study (CPHPUB) cross-sectional study	2006-2008	Morning urine	Children (6-20 y); Female/Male
		COPENHAGEN Puberty Study (CPHPUB) - 129 children substudy	2006-2008	Morning Urine	Children (6-20 y); Female/Male
		RegionH_CPHPUB-129sub_Ig_integration IPCHEM	2006-2014	Morning urine	Children (6-20 y); Female/Male

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Phthalate	Country	Study	Sampling years	Matrix	Stratification
		DEMOCOPHES	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
	Hungary	DEMOCOPHES	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
	Luxembourg	LNS_DEMOCOPHES-LU_Integration IPCHEM	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
	Spain	DEMOCOPHES	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
	Slovenia	DEMOCOPHES	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
	Slovakia	DEMOCOPHES	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
		UKF-mother newborn cohort	2014-2015	Morning urine	Mother (19-42 y) child pairs (1 month)
		SZU-PCBcohort	2014-2017	Morning urine	Teenagers (12-19 y); Female/Male
	Germany	DEMOCOPHES	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
	Sweden	KI_DEMOCOPHES-SE_integration IPCHEM	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
	Poland	NIOM_CDPL (DEMOCOPHES)_integration IPCHEM	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)

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Phthalate	Country	Study	Sampling years	Matrix	Stratification
	Belgium	DEMOCOPHES	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
		FLEHS II - Adolescents - Reference	2008-2009	Morning urine	14-15 years old adolescents; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
		FLEHS III - Adolescents Reference	2013	Spot urine	Teenagers (12-19 y) and different age groups of mothers at birth; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
	Norway	NIPH_IES_integration IPCHEM (Indoor environment)	2011-2017	Morning urine	Mother (32-56 y) and child (6-12 y) pairs
BBzP (MBzP)	Norway	NIPH_IES_integration IPCHEM (Indoor environment)	2011-2017	Morning urine	Mother (32-56 y) and child (6-12 y) pairs
	Czech Republic	Czech HBM Children's exposure (HBM-CE)	2016-2017	Morning urine	Children (5-9 y); Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
		DEMOCOPHES	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
	Denmark	Copenhagen Puberty Study (CPHPUB) cross-sectional study	2006-2008	Morning urine	Children (6-20 y); Female/Male
		RegionH_CPHPUB-129sub_lg_integration IPCHEM	2006-2014	Morning urine	Children (6-20 y); Female/Male
		DEMOCOPHES	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
	Poland	NIOM_CDPL (DEMOCOPHES)_integration IPCHEM	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)

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Phthalate	Country	Study	Sampling years	Matrix	Stratification
	Luxembourg	LNS_DEMOCOPHES-LU_Integration IPCHEM	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
	Hungary	DEMOCOPHES	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
	Spain	DEMOCOPHES	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
	Slovenia	DEMOCOPHES	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
	Slovakia	DEMOCOPHES	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
	Sweden	KI_DEMOCOPHES-SE_integration IPCHEM	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
	Belgium	DEMOCOPHES	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
		FLEHS II - Adolescents - Reference	2008-2009	Morning urine	14-15 years old adolescents; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
		FLEHS III - Adolescents Reference	2013	Spot urine	Teenagers (12-19 y) and different age groups of mothers at birth; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
	Germany	DEMOCOPHES	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)

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Phthalate	Country	Study	Sampling years	Matrix	Stratification
DiBP (MiBP)	Slovenia	DEMOCOPHES	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
	Czech Republic	Czech HBM Children's exposure (HBM-CE)	2016-2017	Morning urine	Children (5-9 y); Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
	Denmark	Copenhagen Puberty Study (CPHPUB) cross-sectional study	2006-2008	Morning urine	Children (6-20 y); Female/Male
		DEMOCOPHES	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
	Belgium	DEMOCOPHES	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
	Slovakia	SZU-PCBcohort	2014-2017	Morning urine	Teenagers (12-19 y); Female/Male
	Poland	NIOM_CDPL (DEMOCOPHES)_integration IPCHEM	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
	Luxembourg	LNS_DEMOCOPHES-LU_Integration IPCHEM	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
	Spain	DEMOCOPHES	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
	Germany	DEMOCOPHES	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
	Norway	NIPH_IES_integration IPCHEM (Indoor environment)	2011-2017	Morning urine	Mother (32-56 y) and child (6-12 y) pairs

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Phthalate	Country	Study	Sampling years	Matrix	Stratification
DnBP (MnBP)	Spain	DEMOCOPHES	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
	Czech Republic	Czech HBM Children's exposure (HBM-CE)	2016-2017	Morning urine	Children (5-9 y); Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
	Denmark	Copenhagen Puberty Study (CPHPUB) cross-sectional study	2006-2008	Morning urine	Children (6-20 y); Female/Male
		UCPH_DK-DEMOCOPHES_integration IPCHEM	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
	Luxembourg	LNS_DEMOCOPHES-LU_Integration IPCHEM	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
	Poland	NIOM_CDPL (DEMOCOPHES)_integration IPCHEM	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
	Norway	NIPH_IES_integration IPCHEM (Indoor environment)	2011-2017	Morning urine	Mother (32-56 y) and child (6-12 y) pairs
	Slovakia	SZU-PCBcohort	2014-2017	Morning urine	Teenagers (12-19 y); Female/Male
		UKF-Mother-newborn cohort	2014-2016	Morning urine	Mother (19-42 y) child pairs (1 month)
	Slovenia	JSI_SLO-DEMOCOPHES_integration IPCHEM	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
	Spain	ISCIII_DEMOCOPHES-SPAIN_integration IPCHEM	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
	Belgium	FLEHS II - Adolescents - Reference	2008-2009	Morning urine	14-15 years old adolescents; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)

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Phthalate	Country	Study	Sampling years	Matrix	Stratification
		FLEHS II - Adult Reference	2008-2009	Morning urine	20-40 years old adults
		VITO_DEMOCOPHES_BE_integration IPCHEM	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
	Germany	DEMOCOPHES	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
DINP (MINP)	Denmark	Copenhagen Mother Child Cohort (CPH-MC)	2006-2007	Spot urine	Children (4-9 y); Female/Male
		Copenhagen Puberty Study (CPHPUB) cross-sectional study	2006-2008	Morning urine	Children (6-20 y); Female/Male
		COPENHAGEN Puberty Study (CPHPUB) - 129 children substudy	2006-2008	Morning urine	Children (6-20 y); Female/Male
		RegionH_CPHPUB-129sub_lg_integration IPCHEM	2006-2014	Morning urine	Children (6-20 y); Female/Male
		DEMOCOPHES	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
DEP (MEP)	Denmark	RegionH_CPHPUB-129sub_lg_integration IPCHEM	2006-2014	Morning urine	Children (6-20 y); Female/Male
		RegionH_CPHPUB-129sub_lg_integration IPCHEM	2006-2014	Morning urine	Children (6-20 y); Female/Male
		Copenhagen Puberty Study (CPHPUB) cross-sectional study	2006-2008	Morning urine	Children (6-20 y); Female/Male
		UCPH_DK-DEMOCOPHES_integration IPCHEM	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
	Poland	NIOM_CDPL (DEMOCOPHES)_integration IPCHEM	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)

Phthalate	Country	Study	Sampling years	Matrix	Stratification
	Hungary	DEMOCOPHES	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
	Spain	DEMOCOPHES	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
	Slovenia	DEMOCOPHES	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
	Sweden	KI_DEMOCOPHES-SE_integration IPCHEM	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
	Luxembourg	LNS_DEMOCOPHES-LU_Integration IPCHEM	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
	Czech Republic	DEMOCOPHES	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
	Belgium	DEMOCOPHES	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
	Slovakia	SZU-PCBcohort	2014-2017	Morning urine	Teenagers (12-19 y); Female/Male
		UKF-mother newborn cohort	2014-2016	Morning urine	Mother (19-42 y) child pairs (1 month)
		UVZ_DEMO_HBM4E UData_integration IPCHEM	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)
	Germany	UBA_DEMOCOPHES-DE_Integration IPCHEM	2011-2012	Morning urine	Mother (18-45 y) and child (6-11 y) pairs; Female/Male; SES (medium/high)

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6.2 Visualisation of HBM-based indicators for phthalates

As this Additional Deliverable is aiming to present for the first time the use of the developed indicator framework, it was decided to focus for phthalate exposure on one representative phthalate. Due to the number of available datasets for DEHP it was decided to elaborate on this substance as illustrative example for showing phthalate indicators. For the work on result indicators the first phase metabolite of DEHP, MEHP, was selected to show differences between countries, age groups, gender and time. In contrast, for the derivation of impact indicators by comparing exposure burden to HBM-GVs, it was relevant to select the respective metabolites of DEHP that are also used for the HBM-GVs. Accordingly, the second-phase metabolites OH-MEHP and oxo-MEHP are selected for further investigation.

Despite the fact that the metabolite MEHP may be easily affected by external contamination and as such, it is normally not as reliable as hydroxy and oxo metabolites, there was a lot of data available and it was used in this deliverable to demonstrate what it is possible to achieve with HBM data.

6.2.1 Result indicator: Possible effectiveness of policy actions in minimising chemical exposure

6.2.1.1 Differences of DEHP exposure over time

Different datasets were available from different sampling periods (years 2008-2016), but no visualisation was envisaged as the datasets are very diverse in size, collected matrix and therefore not harmonised. Comparability was tried but lead to no time trend, thus it was not possible to derive this indicator. From the German Environmental Specimen Bank it is already confirmed that DEHP exposure is decreasing over time as DEHP regulation was in place since 2006 (**Regulation (EC) 1907/2006**) and since 2015 DEHP may only be placed on the EU market or used in the EU if an authorisation has been granted. (Koch et al., 2017).

Table 2: Overview of available datasets within HBM4EU repository sorted by sampling period

Years	Country	Study
2008-2009	Belgium	VITO_FLEHS2RefAdo_integration IPCHEM
		VITO_FLEHS2RefAdult_integration IPCHEM
2011	Hungary	DEMOCOPHES-HU_integration IPCHEM
	Spain	ISCIII_DEMOCOPHES-SPAIN_integration IPCHEM
	Slovenia	JSI_SLO-DEMOCOPHES_integration IPCHEM
	Luxembourg	LNS_DEMOCOPHES-LU_Integration IPCHEM
	Poland	NIOM_CDPL (DEMOCOPHES)_integration IPCHEM
	Czech Republic	NIPH-CZ_DEMOCOPHES-CZ_integration IPCHEM
	Germany	UBA_DEMOCOPHES-DE_Integration IPCHEM
	Denmark	UCPH_DK-DEMOCOPHES_integration IPCHEM
	Slovakia	UVZ_DEMO_HBM4EUData_integration IPCHEM
	Belgium	VITO_DEMOCOPHES_BE_integration IPCHEM
2012	Hungary	DEMOCOPHES-HU_integration IPCHEM
	Sweden	KI_DEMOCOPHES-SE_integration IPCHEM
2015-2016	Slovakia	SZU_PCBcohort_integration IPCHEM

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Conclusions on result indicator for time trends

First trials to use the indicator on available datasets from the HBM4EU repository showed that harmonisation of data is necessary to allow comparison. Illustration of the available P50 values for each dataset was not possible as it would lead to no time trends. It can be assumed that time trends should be illustrated for each country separately, but due to lack of data this was not feasible. Continuous efforts must be undertaken to provide regular input to this indicator and T5.4 will be in contact with WP12 and WP13 to be informed when this data will be available.

6.2.2 Result indicators: Inequality of internal exposure burden

6.2.2.1 Differences of DEHP exposure between countries

Available datasets on MEHP within the repository had the limitation that differences between the countries was only possible by stratification for different age groups (children, adolescents and adults). Therefore Table 3 focuses on data that are available for children (3-11 years), Table 4 comprises data from teenagers (12-19 years old) and Table 5 summarises the data available for adults (20-39 years; 40-59 years).

Table 3: Overview of available repository data on DEHP (MEHP) exposure in different countries for children (DEMOCOPHES data highlighted in colour). Biomarker data in µg/L, not adjusted for urinary dilution (SG). CI=Confidence Interval

Study	Country	N	P50	CI low	CI high
NIPH-CZ_CzechHBM-CE_integration IPCHEM	Czech Republic	148	2,24		2,54
NIPH-CZ_CzechHBM-CE_integration IPCHEM	Czech Republic	223	2,55	2,24	2,85
RegionH_CPHPUB-129sub_integration IPCHEM	Denmark	65	4,81	4,40	6,08
RegionH_CPHPUB-129sub_lg_integration IPCHEM	Denmark	65	5,59	4,37	7,00
RegionH_CPHPUB-Cross_integration IPCHEM	Denmark	913	5,03	4,73	5,33
SZU_PCBcohort_integration IPCHEM	Slovakia	249	4,36	3,73	5,09
DEMOCOPHES-HU_integration IPCHEM	Hungary	120	3,59	3,21	4,35
ISCIII_DEMOCOPHES-SPAIN_integration IPCHEM	Spain	120	6,60	5,47	7,60
JSI_SLO-DEMOCOPHES_integration IPCHEM	Slovenia	119	2,40	2,04	2,90
KI_DEMOCOPHES-SE_integration IPCHEM	Sweden	98	2,84	1,99	3,23
LNS_DEMOCOPHES-LU_Integration IPCHEM	Luxembourg	60	1,70	1,30	2,00
NIOM_CDPL (DEMOCOPHES)_integration IPCHEM	Poland	120	3,65	3,10	4,50
NIPH-CZ_DEMOCOPHES-CZ_integration IPCHEM	Czech Republic	120	3,57	2,64	3,94
UBA_DEMOCOPHES-DE_Integration IPCHEM	Germany	104	2,10	1,89	2,90
UCPH_DK-DEMOCOPHES_integration IPCHEM	Denmark	143	2,01	1,73	2,37
UVZ_DEMO_HBM4EUData_integration IPCHEM	Slovakia	129	4,20	3,59	5,15
VITO_DEMOCOPHES_BE_integration IPCHEM	Belgium	129	2,10	1,80	2,60

Figure 1: Overview of DEHP exposure in morning urine of children between different countries (collected in the years 2016-2017; 2006-2008; 2014-2016; 2011). The error bars represent 95 confidence intervals.

The available datasets on DEHP exposure showed somehow differences in exposure burden between the countries. HBM data on DEHP exposure in children showed significant lowest concentrations in morning urine for Luxembourg from the DEMOCOPHES study (Den Hond et al., 2015). In contrast, Spanish children showed significantly highest exposure burden to DEHP. It is necessary to highlight that only the DEMOCOPHES data are comparable as the other studies are conducted in different years, therefore the low values of the Czech children's exposure study can be explained as this study is the most recent study conducted in 2015-2017 showing significant low values of DEHP exposure in morning urine, compared to their DEMOCOPHES data analysed in 2011. In 2009, the use of DEHP, DnBP, DiBP and BBzP is restricted in plasticised materials of all toys and childcare articles with a concentration limit of 0.1% by entry 51 of Annex XVII to REACH. As DEHP is a regulated substance and new phthalate substitutes are being continuously developed and used from industry in the past years, it can be recommended to compare this indicator with other phthalates/phthalate substitutes.

Table 4: Overview of datasets from the repository for DEHP exposure in adolescents. Biomarker data in µg/L, not adjusted for urinary dilution (SG). CI=Confidence Interval

Country	Study	N	P50	CI low	CI high
Denmark	RegionH_CPHPUB-129sub_lg_integration IPCHEM	61	5,57	1,77	1,39
	RegionH_CPHPUB-129sub_lg_integration IPCHEM	61	3,35	0,50	1,17
	RegionH_CPHPUB-Cross_integration IPCHEM	389	4,54	0,36	0,42
Slovakia	SZU_PCBcohort_integration IPCHEM	65	3,57	1,70	1,28
Belgium	VITO_FLEHS2RefAdo_integration IPCHEM	210	3,75	0,51	0,61

Only a small number of datasets are available for adolescents within the HBM4EU repository. Three countries have collected data for DEHP exposure on adolescents in the past (see Table 4).

Figure 2: Overview of DEHP exposure in morning urine of adolescents between different countries (collected in the years 2006-2008; 2014-2016; 2008-2009). The error bars represent 95 confidence intervals.

Figure 2 shows no differences in DEHP exposure between Denmark, Slovakia and Belgium in adolescents from HBM4EU repository data. As the studies are also conducted in different years (Denmark 2006-2008; Slovakia 2014-2016; Belgium 2008-2009) also no differences can be reported between the different sampling periods on DEHP exposure.

Table 5: Overview of datasets of different countries on DEHP exposure in morning urine of adults

Country	Study	Age category	N	P50 [µg/L]	CI low	CI high
Hungary	DEMOCOPHES-HU_integration IPCHEM	Mothers 20 - 39y	89	4,61	3,18	5,33
Spain	ISCIIII_DEMOCOPHES-SPAIN_integration IPCHEM	Mothers 40 - 59y	75	6,30	5,30	7,80
Slovenia	JSI_SLO-DEMOCOPHES_integration IPCHEM	Mothers 20 - 39y	63	4,80	3,20	6,57
	JSI_SLO-DEMOCOPHES_integration IPCHEM	Mothers 40 - 59y	57	2,80	2,25	3,81
Sweden	KI_DEMOCOPHES-SE_integration IPCHEM	Mothers 20 - 39y	50	3,10	2,06	4,07

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Country	Study	Age category	N	P50 [µg/L]	CI low	CI high
Poland	NIOM_CDPL (DEMOCOPHES)_integration IPCHEM	Mothers 20 - 39y	88	4,85	3,44	5,98
Czech Republic	NIPH-CZ_DEMOCOPHES-CZ_integration IPCHEM	Mothers 20 - 39y	88	3,48	2,96	4,19
Germany	UBA_DEMOCOPHES-DE_Integration IPCHEM	Mothers 20 - 39y	64	3,18	2,44	4,12
	UBA_DEMOCOPHES-DE_Integration IPCHEM	Mothers 40 - 59y	56	1,45	1,01	2,25
Denmark	UCPH_DK-DEMOCOPHES_integration IPCHEM	Mothers 20 - 39y	51	1,79	1,27	2,43
	UCPH_DK-DEMOCOPHES_integration IPCHEM	Mothers 40 - 59y	94	1,57	1,24	2,28
Slovakia	UVZ_DEMO_HBM4EUData_integration IPCHEM	Mothers 20 - 39y	91	4,06	3,16	4,94
Belgium	VITO_DEMOCOPHES_BE_integration IPCHEM	Mothers 20 - 39y	62	2,05	1,38	2,81
	VITO_DEMOCOPHES_BE_integration IPCHEM	Mothers 40 - 59y	67	2,40	2,01	2,70
	VITO_FLEHS2RefAdult_integration IPCHEM	Mothers 20 - 39y	189	2,70	2,30	3,40

Small differences can be identified from Figure 3: Overview of DEHP exposure (P50 values and corresponding CIs) in morning urine of mothers (20-39 years) between different countries (DEMOCOPHES data (2011); Flemish Data FLEHS II RefAdo (2008-2009)) between the countries in the age group of 20-39-year-old mothers. Here, only Denmark and Belgium show lower DEHP exposure burden compared to Hungary, Slovenia, Poland, Czech Republic, Germany, and Slovakia. But no relevant differences in concentrations of DEHP exposure can be reported from this data between the countries.

Figure 3: Overview of DEHP exposure (P50 values and corresponding CIs) in morning urine of mothers (20-39 years) between different countries (DEMOCOPHES data (2011); Flemish Data FLEHS II RefAdo (2008-2009))

Figure 4 with DEMOCOPHES data shows higher values of DEHP exposure in morning urine of Spanish women (40-59 years old) in contrast to Slovenia, Germany, Denmark and Belgium. No other country differences can be identified.

Figure 4: Overview of DEMOCOPHES data (P50 values and corresponding CIs) on DEHP exposure in morning urine of adult women (40-59 years old) between different countries

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Conclusions on result indicator regarding country differences

Inequality of exposure burden between countries can be interpreted with the analysis of datasets from the HBM4EU repository. With the well-harmonised and aggregated DEMOCOPHES data it could be highlighted that DEHP exposure in Spanish children and their mothers is higher compared to other selected countries. With this result indicator it can be endorsed that targeted recommendation for action and information on exposure sources and routes may help Spanish citizens to minimise exposure burden from DEHP. Further recommendations for action for policy makers might also be considered to further minimise exposure burden in the population. In contrast, Luxembourg was highlighted of having the smallest exposure burden from DEHP in their population. But it needs to be emphasised that the sample size of Luxembourg with N=60 is very small compared to the other sample sizes and might influence the results of small exposure burden. The influence of the socioeconomic status might also be a relevant aspect that needs to be further analysed.

Finally, with the illustrative examples on DEHP exposure it can be concluded that the HBM-based result indicator is suitable for showing country differences in exposure burden to finally highlight significant differences that may lead to targeted actions for minimising exposure burden in the respective countries.

6.2.2.2 Differences of DEHP exposure between age groups

For the differentiation of age groups, it was only possible to stratify for each dataset within the repository, showing equal results compared to the country differences, but another visualisation of the indicator was chosen to highlight the different perspectives of this indicator.

Table 6: Overview of available datasets in HBM4EU repository regarding different age groups on DEHP exposure. Biomarker data in µg/L, not adjusted for urinary dilution (SG). CI=Confidence Interval

Country	Study	Age category	N	P50	CI low	CI high
Hungary	DEMOCOPHES-HU_integration IPCHEM	Mothers 20 - 39y	89	4,61	3,18	5,33
	DEMOCOPHES-HU_integration IPCHEM	Children 6 - 11y	120	3,59	3,21	4,35
Spain	ISCIIII_DEMOCOPHES-SPAIN_integration IPCHEM	Mothers 40 - 59y	75	6,30	5,30	7,80
	ISCIIII_DEMOCOPHES-SPAIN_integration IPCHEM	Children 6 - 11y	120	6,60	5,47	7,60
Slovenia	JSI_SLO-DEMOCOPHES_integration IPCHEM	Mothers 20 - 39y	63	4,80	3,20	6,57
	JSI_SLO-DEMOCOPHES_integration IPCHEM	Mothers 40 - 59y	57	2,80	2,25	3,81
	JSI_SLO-DEMOCOPHES_integration IPCHEM	Children 6 - 11y	119	2,40	2,04	2,90
Sweden	KI_DEMOCOPHES-SE_integration IPCHEM	Mothers 20 - 39y	50	3,10	2,06	4,07
	KI_DEMOCOPHES-SE_integration IPCHEM	Children 6 - 11y	98	2,84	1,99	3,23

Country	Study	Age category	N	P50	CI low	CI high
Luxembourg	LNS_DEMOCOPHES-LU_Integration IPCHEM	Children 6 - 11y	60	1,70	1,30	2,00
Poland	NIOM_CDPL (DEMOCOPHES)_integration IPCHEM	Mothers 20 - 39y	88	4,85	3,44	5,98
	NIOM_CDPL (DEMOCOPHES)_integration IPCHEM	Children 6 - 11y	120	3,65	3,10	4,50
Czech Republic	NIPH-CZ_DEMOCOPHES-CZ_integration IPCHEM	Mothers 20 - 39y	88	3,48	2,96	4,19
	NIPH-CZ_DEMOCOPHES-CZ_integration IPCHEM	Children 6 - 11y	120	3,57	2,64	3,94
Germany	UBA_DEMOCOPHES-DE_Integration IPCHEM	Mothers 20 - 39y	64	3,18	2,44	4,12
	UBA_DEMOCOPHES-DE_Integration IPCHEM	Mothers 40 - 59y	56	1,45	1,01	2,25
	UBA_DEMOCOPHES-DE_Integration IPCHEM	Children 6 - 11y	104	2,10	1,89	2,90
Denmark	UCPH_DK-DEMOCOPHES_integration IPCHEM	Mothers 20 - 39y	51	1,79	1,27	2,43
	UCPH_DK-DEMOCOPHES_integration IPCHEM	Mothers 40 - 59y	94	1,57	1,24	2,28
	UCPH_DK-DEMOCOPHES_integration IPCHEM	Children 6 - 11y	143	2,01	1,73	2,37
Slovakia	UVZ_DEMO_HBM4EUData_integration IPCHEM	Adults 20 - 39y	91	4,06	3,16	4,94
	UVZ_DEMO_HBM4EUData_integration IPCHEM	Children 6 - 11y	129	4,20	3,59	5,15
Belgium	VITO_DEMOCOPHES_BE_integration IPCHEM	Mothers 20 - 39y	62	2,05	1,38	2,81
	VITO_DEMOCOPHES_BE_integration IPCHEM	Mothers 40 - 59y	67	2,40	2,01	2,70
	VITO_DEMOCOPHES_BE_integration IPCHEM	Children 6 - 11y	129	2,10	1,80	2,60

Differences of DEHP exposure for the age group 6-11 years are seen for the country Luxembourg that shows the lowest DEHP concentration in morning urine. Spain showed the highest DEHP concentrations in children (6-11 years old) and women (40-59 years old) in contrast to the other countries. For women of the age group 20-39 no clear differences can be reported. In women between 40-59 years of age also Spain showed highest exposure burden to DEHP in contrast to the other countries (see Figure 5).

Figure 5: Overview of DEHP exposure in morning urine of different age groups

Conclusions on result indicator regarding age differences

With the present data it could be shown that the result indicator is relevant to illustrate inequality in exposure burden, as stratification for different age groups is possible. With these results targeted research can be undertaken to interpret the reasons for having higher exposure burden in one age group compared to the other. Making use of this indicator enables to realise more focused and straightforward research on relevant age groups of high exposure burden, which finally may help to understand differences in behaviour or lifestyle related to certain age groups that may lead to higher exposure.

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6.2.2.3 Sex differences

Stratification for sex was done with the DEMOCOPHES data from children between 6 and 11 years. Table 7 gives an overview of the available datasets within the repository that allowed this stratification.

Table 7: Overview of DEMOCOPHES data within HBM4EU repository stratified for sex (female/male). Biomarker data in µg/L, not adjusted for urinary dilution (SG). CI=Confidence Interval

Sex	Study	N	P50	CI low	CI high
Female	DEMOCOPHES-HU_integration IPCHEM	60	3,23	2,18	3,63
	ISCIIII_DEMOCOPHES-SPAIN_integration IPCHEM	60	6,40	5,20	7,20
	JSI_SLO-DEMOCOPHES_integration IPCHEM	60	2,40	1,80	3,48
	KI_DEMOCOPHES-SE_integration IPCHEM	51	3,95	3,30	5,50
	NIOM_CDPL (DEMOCOPHES)_integration IPCHEM	60	3,31	2,31	3,80
	NIPH-CZ_DEMOCOPHES-CZ_integration IPCHEM	61	2,40	1,83	3,28
	UBA_DEMOCOPHES-DE_Integration IPCHEM	60	1,76	1,40	2,28
	UCPH_DK-DEMOCOPHES_integration IPCHEM	73	4,16	3,10	4,98
	UVZ_DEMO_HBM4EUData_integration IPCHEM	63	1,90	1,60	2,57
	VITO_DEMOCOPHES_BE_integration IPCHEM	63	2,60	1,95	3,27
Male	DEMOCOPHES-HU_integration IPCHEM	60	4,93	3,57	6,16
	ISCIIII_DEMOCOPHES-SPAIN_integration IPCHEM	60	7,10	5,20	8,98
	JSI_SLO-DEMOCOPHES_integration IPCHEM	60	2,45	2,00	3,10
	NIOM_CDPL (DEMOCOPHES)_integration IPCHEM	60	3,10	2,70	4,50
	NIPH-CZ_DEMOCOPHES-CZ_integration IPCHEM	59	3,94	2,64	4,58
	UBA_DEMOCOPHES-DE_Integration IPCHEM	60	2,21	1,88	3,10
	UCPH_DK-DEMOCOPHES_integration IPCHEM	70	2,32	1,84	3,08
	UVZ_DEMO_HBM4EUData_integration IPCHEM	66	4,55	3,57	6,83
	VITO_DEMOCOPHES_BE_integration IPCHEM	66	2,30	1,80	3,03

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No sex differences were seen between female and male DEHP exposure in children from DEMOCOPHES data (see Figure 6)

Figure 6: Illustration of the result indicator regarding sex differences based on DEMOCOPHES data

Conclusions of the result indicator on sex differences

The illustrative example of the result indicator on sex differences confirmed that differences of exposure burden between male and female can help to highlight inequalities in exposure burden that asks for targeted research to identify reasons for these differences. Results of this analysis may help to provide recommendations for citizens or policy makers to prevent those inequalities.

6.2.3 Impact indicator: Health relevance of internal exposure burden

The impact indicator “health relevance of internal exposure burden” compares internal exposure burden to certain chemicals to their available HBM-GVs.

6.2.3.1 Health relevance of DEHP exposure in children

Task 5.2 within HBM4EU aims to derive Human Biomonitoring health-based guidance values (HBM-GVs) for prioritised substances (Apel et al., 2020). Under this task, HBM-GV for DEHP (Sum of OH-MEHP and oxo-MEHP) has been derived for children, resulting in an HBM-GVchildren of 340 µg/L (see HBM4EU [Deliverable 5.2 “1st substance-group specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values”](#)).

Figure 7: Impact indicator for DEHP exposure (P95 values) in children between different countries (DEMOCOPHES data, 2011)

The impact indicator for DEHP exposure assumes no health impacts for children regarding the DEMOCOPHES data from 2011. The indicator foresees to make use of a calculation to estimate health risks (see Table 8). Therefore, the P95 value is divided by the respective HBM-GV of the substance, which leads to values where no health impact is being expected according to current data (<1), or where health impacts cannot be excluded according to current data (>1).

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Table 8: Calculation and interpretation of impact indicator for DEHP exposure for children

Study	P95/HBM-GV	Interpretation
DEMOCOPHES-HU_integration IPCHEM	0,75	Values < 1; At least 95% of sampled children of DEMOCOPHES data show internal exposures below the HBM-GV for DEHP (Σ OH-MEHP and oxo-MEHP). Therefore, no health impacts regarding DEHP exposure are being expected according to this data.
ISCIII_DEMOCOPHES-SPAIN_integration IPCHEM	0,59	
JSI_SLO-DEMOCOPHES_integration IPCHEM	0,37	
KI_DEMOCOPHES-SE_integration IPCHEM	0,50	
LNS_DEMOCOPHES-LU_Integration IPCHEM	0,17	
NIOM_CDPL (DEMOCOPHES)_integration IPCHEM	0,64	
NIPH-CZ_DEMOCOPHES-CZ_integration IPCHEM	0,57	
UBA_DEMOCOPHES-DE_Integration IPCHEM	0,30	
UCPH_DK-DEMOCOPHES_integration IPCHEM	0,38	
UVZ_DEMO_HBM4EUData_integration IPCHEM	0,77	
VITO_DEMOCOPHES_BE_integration IPCHEM	0,52	

Table 8 shows the calculation of health risks for the impact indicator. For DEHP exposure in children it can be confirmed that no health impacts are being expected for children according to the DEMOCOPHES data.

6.2.3.2 Health relevance of DEHP exposure in adults

A HBM-GV for DEHP exposure to adults was derived under Task 5.2. The HBM-GV for DEHP (Sum of OH-MEHP and oxo-MEHP) exposure for adults in urine is 500 µg/L.

Figure 8: Impact indicator for DEHP exposure in adults between different countries (DEMOCOPHES data, 2011)

The impact indicator for DEHP exposure in adults showed no related health impacts based on DEMOCOPHES data from 2011. In a next step, also the health risks have been calculated.

Table 9: Calculation and interpretation of impact indicator for DEHP exposure for adults

Study	P95/HBM-GV	Interpretation
DEMOCOPHES-HU_integration IPCHEM	0,25	Values < 1; At least 95% of sampled mothers of DEMOCOPHES data show internal exposures below HBM-GV. Therefore, no health impacts regarding DEHP exposure are being expected according to this data.
ISCIII_DEMOCOPHES-SPAIN_integration IPCHEM	0,25	
JSI_SLO-DEMOCOPHES_integration IPCHEM	0,23	
KI_DEMOCOPHES-SE_integration IPCHEM	0,14	
LNS_DEMOCOPHES-LU_Integration IPCHEM	0,07	
NIOM_CDPL (DEMOCOPHES)_integration IPCHEM	0,30	
NIPH-CZ_DEMOCOPHES-CZ_integration IPCHEM	0,22	
UBA_DEMOCOPHES-DE_Integration IPCHEM	0,12	
UCPH_DK-DEMOCOPHES_integration IPCHEM	0,21	
UVZ_DEMO_HBM4EUData_integration IPCHEM	0,24	
VITO_DEMOCOPHES_BE_integration IPCHEM	0,17	

Table 9 shows that no health impacts are being expected from DEHP exposure on adults (all values < 1) according to the DEMOCOPHES data from 2011.

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Conclusions on impact indicator

The indicators on health relevance for DEHP exposure on adults and children regarding internal chemical exposure were derived. The values from internal chemical exposure for either children or adults were below the HBM-GVs for DEHP, thus currently no health risks regarding DEHP exposure are being expected based on the actual database (DEMOCOPHES data, 2011) as DEHP is regulated since 2006. However, it has to be highlighted that more recent and harmonised data are necessary to verify this interpretation and also other less regulated phthalates or phthalate substitutes might be relevant to consider when evaluating health risks from endocrine disrupting chemicals. Nevertheless, with the illustrative examples it could be demonstrated that the impact indicator is relevant to highlight exposure burden related to health risks to finally set priorities for further actions.

7 HBM-based indicators for BPA exposure

7.1 Geographical coverage

Figure 9 below presents the geographical coverage of HBM data of BPA. Data include morning (98%) as well as spot urine samples which may slightly increase variability. However due to a constant daily intake, steady state concentrations in urine can be reached. Overall concentrations across countries were close together as already reported by (Covaci et al., 2015). In Slovenia relatively larger concentrations were observed in children compared to adults. Overall, concentrations between children and adults were quite similar (Covaci et al., 2015).

Figure 9: HBM data for BPA (P50) based on DEMOCOPHES data. (BE=Belgium, DK=Denmark, LU=Luxembourg, SI=Slovenia, ES=Spain, SE=Sweden)

7.2 Differences in HBM data by age, sex and ISCED

Differences in age are reported in the previous section. Levels were quite similar between adults and children (excl. Slovenia & Norway). For differences by ISCED, the amount of data was scarce in the repository. Covaci et al. (2015) reported in a multivariate model that education may be a significant determinant for BPA concentrations, but the trend was unclear. More data on the difference between urinary BPA concentrations and ISCED is necessary to make robust conclusions.

For sex, observations are presented in the figure below. The ratio of the concentration in males versus females is presented for the P50 and in units of µg/L and µg/g creatinine. Based on µg/L, males tend to have higher BPA concentrations than females but when corrected for creatinine this difference seems to disappear. However, in international literature, higher concentrations of BPA are reported in male versus female based on androgen-related metabolism (Takeuchi and Tsutsumi, 2002; Caporossi and Papaleo, 2015).

Figure 10: Ratio of BPA concentrations in male versus female at P50 in units of $\mu\text{g/L}$ and $\mu\text{g/g crea}$. Results include DEMOCOPHES data and other datasets. DEMOCOPHES data unless noted differently. BE*: FLEHSII; BE: FLEHSIII; IL*: MOH-IL_IBS. The dashed line (=1) presents an equal concentration of BPA between male and female. (DK=Denmark, ES=Spain, SI=Slovenia, BE=Belgium, IL=Israel).**

7.3 Time trends

No data for BPA are available in the HBM4EU repository regarding time trends.

7.4 HBM BPA data in a risk context

BPA is a substance of very high concern (SVHC). A large amount of information on the toxicity of low doses of BPA is available. However, there are still uncertainties on the effects (Pollock et al., 2021).

Figure 11 and Figure 12 below present the available HBM data in a risk context. HBM-GV were derived in the HBM4EU project based on kidney weight as critical effect.

Figure 11: HBM data for BPA (P95) in children including DEMOCOPHES data and other datasets. DEMOCOPHES data unless noted differently. *: no DEMOCOPHES data (AT: EAA_PBAT; NO: NIPH_IES). Dashed line presents the HBM4EU guidance value (137 µg/L). All campaigns ran in the period 2010-2014. (AT=Austria, BE=Belgium, DK=Denmark, ES=Spain, LU=Luxembourg, NO=Norway, SE=Sweden, SI=Slovenia).

Figure 12: HBM data for BPA (P95) in adults including DEMOCOPHES data and other datasets. DEMOCOPHES data unless noted differently. *: no DEMOCOPHES data (IL: MOH-IL_IBS; NO: NIPH_IES). Dashed line presents the HBM4EU guidance value (233 µg/L). All campaigns ran in the period 2010-2014. (BE=Belgium, DK=Denmark, ES=Spain, IL=Israel, LU=Luxembourg, NO=Norway, SE=Sweden, SI=Slovenia).

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8 HBM-based indicators for PFAS exposure

In September this year (2020), the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) set a new safety threshold for four of the most commonly found PFAS. This group of substances is also called “forever chemicals” as they do not break down in the environment². Perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA), perfluorooctane sulfonate (PFOS), perfluorononanoic acid (PFNA) and perfluorohexane sulfonic acid (PFHxS) currently have a new tolerable weekly intake (TWI) of 4.4 nanograms per kilogram of body weight (sum of PFOS, PFOA, PFNA, PFHxS). These four chemicals are all listed as substances of very high concern (SVHC) under the EU’s REACH regime and are therefore associated with serious risks for human health. They also make up an estimated 46 % of Europeans’ exposure to perfluoroalkyl (PFAS).

EFSA has derived a serum level HB-GV set at 6.9 ng/mL in mothers at 35 years of age for the sum of PFOS, PFOA, PFNA, PFHxS.

In the highlight of this, and to be able to draw indicators on health relevance, the data presented for all the indicators in section 5 will be based on data for the sum of these 4 PFAS, in blood or serum samples of adult women.

8.1 Result indicator: Temporal increase or stabilisation of internal exposure possibly related to policy action

The data in the repository is very diverse, be it in terms of collected matrix (blood plasma, blood serum, cord blood-plasma, breast milk) to the size of each dataset. Therefore, it was not possible to harmonise the data and derive this indicator and hence not possible to check for the effectiveness of policy actions in minimising chemical exposure.

8.2 Result indicator: Possible effectiveness of policy actions in minimising chemical exposure

For the same reasons stated in the section above, this indicator could not be derived. Therefore, it was not possible to see if any decrease of substance concentration was possibly related with efficient policy actions.

8.3 Result indicators: Inequality of internal exposure burden

8.3.1 Age, sex & country differences for PFHxS, PFNA, PFOA & PFOS

For this indicator, seeing that the chosen matrix was blood serum, there are only a few datasets available and therefore the data visualisation was combined for this group of substances.

² [‘Forever chemicals’: EFSA slashes PFAS exposure limits \(endseurope.com\)](https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/news/forever-chemicals)

Figure 13: Country exposure coverage of PFHxS in adults (M: males, F: females) for the age groups of 20-39 and 40-59 years old. P50 values in blood serum (g/L)

Figure 14: Country exposure coverage of PFNA in adults (M: males, F: females) for the age groups of 20-39 and 40-59 years old. P50 values in blood serum (g/L)

Figure 15: Country exposure coverage of PFOA in adults (M: males, F: females) for the age groups of 20-39 and 40-59 years old, and teenagers (12-19 yo). P50 values in blood serum (µg/L)

Figure 16: Country exposure coverage of PFOS in adults (M: males, F: females) for the age groups of 20-39 and 40-59 years old, and teenagers (12-19 yo). P50 values in blood serum (µg/L)

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Conclusions

With so few datasets for the PFAS of interest, it is difficult to know how robust these indicators are, and therefore the conclusions taken from them.

There is a high exposure level of PFHxS in the Belgian population from 40-59 yo, but seeing we do not have similar data for other age groups for this substance we cannot draw any conclusions as to whether or not this population range is more exposed, or if the Belgian population is more exposed than other countries overall.

PFOS and PFOA are the most regulated PFAS, so it is natural to see a decline in concentration ranging from 2008-2015. PFOS was added to the Annex B of the Stockholm Convention in 2009, the European Commission removed PFOS from REACH annex xvii and added it to the Annex I of the Regulation (EC) No 850/2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council on persistent organic pollutants. PFOA and its precursors were restricted under the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH) regulation (EU, 2006), including their presence in products made or imported into the EU. Due to the high interest these legacy chemicals have, the EU has currently developed a Chemicals' Strategy which includes a set of guidelines for PFAS.

8.3.2 Adult females' coverage for PFHxS, PFNA, PFOA & PFOS

Seeing the data sought was only for blood serum in adult females, we were left with 3 datasets from Denmark (2010-2012) and one or two datasets from VITO for 2008 and 2014 (Figure 17: Geographical coverage of PFHxS in adult women (20-39 and 40-59 years old). P50 values in blood serum (g/mL) to Figure 20: Geographical coverage of PFOS in adult women (20-39 and 40-59 years old). P50 values in blood serum (g/L)). It is therefore possible to see the differences in exposure between countries for which the datasets were available.

Figure 17: Geographical coverage of PFHxS in adult women (20-39 and 40-59 years old). P50 values in blood serum (g/mL)

Figure 18: Geographical coverage of PFNA in adult women (20-39 and 40-59 years old). P50 values in blood serum (g/L)

Figure 19: Geographical coverage of PFOA in adult women (20-39 and 40-59 years old). P50 values in blood serum (g/L)

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Figure 20: Geographical coverage of PFOS in adult women (20-39 and 40-59 years old). P50 values in blood serum (g/L)

8.3.3 ISCED for PFHxS, PFNA, PFOA & PFOS

Not enough data was available to produce a robust indicator visualisation.

8.4 Health relevance of PFHxS, PFNA, PFOA & PFOS

The HBM4EU project did not derive HBM-GV for the PFAS group as initially foreseen as EFSA had derived their own (external) HBGV (EFSA, 2020) and therefore HBM4EU could infer what a potential HBM-GV would be.

From that document:

“The CONTAM Panel identified a new study with children from Germany showing an inverse association between serum levels of PFOA, but also the sum of PFOA, PFNA, PFHxS and PFOS, and antibody titres against haemophilus influenzae type b (Hib), diphtheria and tetanus in serum sampled from 1-year-old children, predominantly breastfed. A lowest BMDL10 of 17.5 ng/mL at the age of 1 year was derived for the sum of PFOA, PFNA, PFHxS and PFOS, based on the inverse association between serum levels of the sum of these four PFASs and antibody titres against diphtheria.

*This BMDL10 was used to estimate the daily intake by mothers that would result in this critical serum concentration at 1 year of age in breastfed children. Using a PBPK model, and assuming 12 months of breastfeeding, it was estimated that the BMDL10 in infants corresponds to an intake by the mother of 0.63 ng/kg bw per day for the sum of the four PFASs. **Such intake would result in a serum level in the mother at 35 years of age of 6.9 ng/mL.***

The CONTAM Panel decided to use the daily intake of 0.63 ng/kg bw per day as the starting point and established a group tolerable weekly intake (TWI) of $7 \times 0.63 = 4.4$ ng/kg bw per week for the sum of PFOA, PFNA, PFHxS and PFOS.”

To clarify, EFSA does not derive internal limit values and therefore this is not a HBM-GV. However, when there are HBM measurement data available, as is the case for these 4 PFAS, it is possible to present an internal level that corresponds to the TDI or TWI. In this specific case, it refers to the TWI for the group of 4 PFAS.

Therefore, EFSA has derived a serum level HB-GV set at 6.9 ng/mL for the sum of the 4 PFAS, in mothers at 35 years of age.

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The new 'safe limit' for weekly intake is significantly lower than EFSA's original proposal of eight nanograms per kilogram of body weight, with the agency citing the "decreased response of the immune system to vaccination to be the most critical human health effect" associated with the four substances. For a more detailed overview, please see Table 10.

Table 10: Sum of PFHxS, PFNA, PFOA and PFOS' P95 values for bloods serum in adult women between 20-39 years old. Disclaimer: These values were done by doing the sum of the P95 for the 4 PFAS, assuming a worst-case scenario for which an individual has the same ranking for each of the PFAS which is not a realistic scenario.

Country	Blood Serum (microg/L) P95				Sum of the 4 PFAS	(ng/mL)		Comments
	PFHxS	PFNA	PFOA	PFOS		HB-GV (EFSA)	P95/HB-GV	
Denmark 2010 (20-39 yo)	0.59	1.27	4.62	17.36	23.84	6.90	3.45	Value > 1 indicates that the 95 th percentile is above the health-based guidance value. The higher the value above 1, the larger the probability of health impact.
Denmark 2011 (20-39 yo)	0.69	1.56	4.05	14.81	21.10	6.90	3.06	
Denmark 2012 (20-39 yo)	0.54	1.03	3.62	15.73	20.93	6.90	3.03	
Belgium 2008 (20-39 yo)			5.97	29.39	35.35	6.90	5.12	

Conclusion

Using the P95 sum of the 4 PFAS, the value is 3 to 5 times higher than the derived HB-GV from EFSA. We assumed a worst-case scenario situation and summed the P95 for the 4 PFAS, whereas in a real situation an individual may have a high value of exposure to PFOS but not to PFOA.

Based on the HBM-I value of PFOS and the HBM-I value of PFOA, PFAS' health effects cannot be ruled out (Buekers et al., 2018). Therefore, the probability of a health impact due to PFAS exposure is high, and the information available is of relevance to policy makers to set priorities for further action.

9 HBM-based indicators for cadmium exposure

The current deliverable focusses on urinary Cd. The advantages of looking into urinary Cd are that it is a marker for long-term exposure, the temporal stability is large regarding spot - or morning urine collections (Vacchi-Suzzi et al., 2015) and more data is available when compared to blood Cd (e.g. urinary Cd in DEMOCOPHES study).

9.1 Geographical coverage

Cd is a non-essential element that accumulates in the body (e.g. kidney) over time. Urinary Cd concentrations are therefore larger in adults than in children. When looking at geographical differences, it's remarkable that concentrations in adults in Poland are relatively larger compared to other countries. This can be related to national Cd emissions to air which was larger for Poland than for other EU countries and associated with urinary Cd. Also higher concentrations of Cd in food may play a role (Smolders et al., 2015). Another reason could be the historical use of fertilisers with relatively higher Cd content (Berglund et al., 2015; WHO, 2015) currently being looked into by our Cd Chemical Group Leaders at Jožef Stefan Institute in Slovenia.

Figure 21: Urinary Cd concentrations for different EU countries. Most of the data are from the DEMOCOPHES dataset (mothers and children) except countries with an asterisk (LT: LSMU_BCAS2). Data collection campaigns cover approximately the same years, covering the period 2010-2014. For DK the Cd concentration in children was set at the LOQ. As well smoking as non-smoking adults are included.

9.2 Differences in HBM data by age, sex and ISCED

Differences by age were discussed in previous paragraph. For sex, it has been shown in the international literature that cadmium concentrations are relatively higher in females than in males (Adams and Newcomb, 2014; Vacchi-Suzzi et al., 2015), which is probably related to lower iron levels in females and increased gastrointestinal absorption.

For ISCED, urinary Cd concentrations in mothers of the DEMOCOPHES project showed in general larger concentrations in adult women with lower education compared to higher education. This type of social inequalities was recently published in a report by the WHO (Buekers et al., 2019).

Figure 22: Average concentration (geometric mean) of cadmium in mother's urine by education level, 2011–2012. Note that low and high education can represent different education categories across countries. Source: data from DEMOCOPHES country-specific statistical analysis reports.

9.3 Time trends

From the repository data only one-time trend analysis can be performed i.e. for the Czech Republic (dataset: NIPHPrague_CzechHBM-AE). This dataset includes urinary data for adults for the years 2007, 2009, 2015 and 2018. The percentage of male participants was rather stable over the years. Both age categories 20-39 years old and 40-59 years old (here on defined as "y") show a decrease in Cd concentrations for the P50. When looking at the percentage smokers in the total of participants, there is a decreasing trend certainly for the age group 40-59 y which could have some influence in the urinary Cd levels.

Education classification of the participants did not change drastically except for the year 2015, where in proportion less participants with low education were recruited (age category 40-59 y). Overall, it can be concluded that there is a downward trend in urinary Cd concentrations over time.

Figure 23: Cd concentrations in Czech Republic (dataset: NIPHPrague_CzechHBM-AE). Age category: 20-39y adults. On the left Y-axis the P50 concentrations are presented whereas on the right Y-axis the fraction of current smokers

Figure 24: Cd concentrations in Czech Republic (dataset: NIPHPrague_CzechHBM-A). Age category: 40-59y adults. On the left Y-axis the P50 concentrations are presented whereas on the right Y-axis the fraction of current smokers.

9.4 HBM Cd data in a risk context

In 2009, the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) performed a risk assessment for dietary Cd exposure by comparing the calculated dietary Cd exposures of the EU general population with the recommended TWI (Tolerable Weekly Intake) of 2.5 µg/kg bw based on kidney function (EFSA, 2009). Conclusions were that the mean Cd exposure for adults across Europe was close to, or slightly exceeding the TWI. The exposure of some subgroups of the population, such as vegetarians, children, smokers and people living in highly contaminated areas was determined to exceed the TWI by about 2-fold. As the TWI is based on an early indicator of changes in kidney function and not on actual kidney damage, the risk for adverse effects on kidney function at dietary exposure across Europe was considered low at the individual level. Nevertheless, EFSA concluded that the current exposure to Cd at the population level should be reduced (EFSA, 2009; EFSA, 2012).

Based on HBM data following conclusions could be made: the HBM guidance value used to consider the urinary Cd concentrations in a risk-based context equals 1 µg/g creatinine at the age of >51y (HBM4EU-guidance value). Based on PBPK modelling³ **alert Cd values** were derived for different age categories seeing the accumulation of Cd over time. From the figures below it can be seen that for children P95 values for most countries exceed the alert values. For adults, this was less clear as for different age categories, different alert values exist (<= 10y: 0.1 µg Cd/g crea; 11-20y: 0.2 µg Cd/g crea; 21-30y: 0.3 µg Cd/g crea; 31-40y: 0.5 µg Cd/g crea; 41-50y: 0.8 µg Cd/g crea; >51y: 1 µg Cd/g crea) and these do not correspond perfectly with the age categories in the repository (certainly 40-59y). Also based on the alert values these differ significantly for a person of 40y compared to a person of 41 y. Therefore, a band representing the alert value for adults was applied. It is clear that for adults in Poland the alert value is exceeded.

Figure 25: Urinary Cd data in DEMOCOPHES children. The dashed line represents the alert value for children based on the HBM4EU HBMGV at the age of >51y (1 µg Cd/g crea) and PBPK modelling

³ 8-compartment human PBPK model by (Kjellström and Nordberg 1978) for Cd, that was recently refined by the introduction of equations describing the French general population mean body weight and creatinine excretion evolutions according to age, was considered (Leconte et al. 2020, submitted).

Figure 26: Urinary Cd data in DEMOCOPHES & other datasets in adults. Data for Spain (*) are from the BIOAMBIENTES dataset (2005-2014) and present male and females. The gray horizontal band presents the alert value for adults (21-40y) based on an HBM4EU guidance values at the age of 21-40y (0.3 to 0.5 µg Cd/g crea) and PBPk modelling.

Figure 27: Urinary Cd data in DEMOCOPHES and other datasets in adults. Data for the Czech Republic are from the NIPHPrague_CzechHBM-AE study (2009) and present male and females. The gray band represents the alert value for adults (31 to ≥51y) based on an HBM4EU guidance values at the age of 31 to >51y (0.5 to 1 µg Cd/g crea) and PBPk modelling.

10 HBM-based indicators for aprotic solvents exposure

Aprotic solvents, such as N-methyl-pyrrolidone (NMP) and N-ethyl-pyrrolidone (NEP), are selected as prioritised substances under HBM4EU. Therefore, also HBM based indicators were planned.

HBM-GVs have been derived under Task 5.2. These values will be used for further visualisation of impact indicators when new HBM data become available. For both, NMP and NEP, HBM-GV for the general population have been derived and resulted in values of 15 mg/L for adults and 10 mg/L for children in urine for the sum of the metabolites 5-HNMP and 2-HMSI for NMP, and for the sum of 5-HNEP and 2-HESI for NEP. Only concentrations of separate metabolites for the German Environmental Specimen Bank (ESB) were available in the repository and not for the sum of metabolites (N=60; age range 20-39 years old). Based on these data, information could be gathered about differences between sexes and time trends. It is clear that for the metabolites 5-hydroxy-N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (HNMP) and 2-hydroxy-N-methylsuccinimide (HMSI), concentrations do not change over time. When expressed in $\mu\text{g/L}$, no difference was noticed between males and females whereas when expressed in $\mu\text{g/g}$ creatinine, concentrations were larger in females compared males.

Figure 28: 5-HNMP in German students (ESB data; unit $\mu\text{g/L}$)

Figure 29: 5-HNMP in German students (ESB data; unit µg/g creat)

Figure 30: 2-HMSI in German students (ESB data; unit µg/L)

Figure 31: 2-HMSI in German students (ESB data; unit µg/g creat)

From the repository it's not clear how much of the concentrations of 5-hydroxy-N-ethyl-2-pyrrolidone (5-HNEP) are below the detection limit.

For the metabolite 2-hydroxy-N-ethylsuccinimide (2-HESI) there is a clear increase of the urinary concentrations over time as well for males and females.

Figure 32: 2-HESI in German students (ESB data; unit µg/L)

Figure 33: 2-HESI in German students (ESB data; unit µg/g creat)

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11 Conclusions

This Additional Deliverable provides preliminary illustrative examples of the HBM-based indicators and how they might help to interpret research results and highlight needs for further actions.

For these visualisations, a first step was to give a description of the currently available datasets of the selected substance (groups) phthalates, bisphenol A, cadmium, PFAS (PFHxS, PFNA, PFOA and PFOS) and aprotic solvents from the HBM4EU repository (Status July 2020). In a second step, indicator visualisation and interpretation have been performed and the outcomes of the indicator are explained.

Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden. In the most recent Additional Deliverable (AD5.3), a framework for the derivation of indicators was developed comprising aspects such as visualisation, calculation and interpretation. Within this task, policy questions have also been collected for each substance (group) to demonstrate which questions the indicators are able to answer.

As still only a limited number of datasets are available in the HBM4EU repository, comparison of the data is still a delicate issue in what concerns different quality aspects discussed in the last Additional Deliverable. For the phthalates, it was therefore decided to mainly base the visualisation of indicators on harmonised data such as the DEMOCOPHES data. But nevertheless, with these first examples it could be shown that the developed HBM-based indicators are a useful tool to highlight differences between countries, or inequalities in age groups or sexes, changes in exposure burden over time, and even to help classify health risks which is useful in a prioritisation and regulatory setting. The use of these indicators may help policy makers in the future to make targeted priority setting for research or to discover further needs for actions based on HBM data.

For the next year, it is planned to make use of the harmonised and quality assured data from the aligned studies carried out under work package 8 within HBM4EU. This harmonised and most recent data on exposure burden of European citizens for selected substances, may provide robust indicators that will show if policy actions already in place resulted in minimised internal chemical exposure, if there are inequalities in exposure regarding age, sex, educational level, or between countries, and if this internal exposure may have a health impact.

With the use of the HBM-based indicators on the data of the aligned studies it will be possible, for the first time, to give a very recent overview and data interpretation of the actual exposure burden of European citizens that may help for any future priority setting for chemicals regulation.

For future work, it can be recommended that a platform where these indicators are easily accessible and visualisation is automatically provided may help for advanced and better interpretation of HBM data.

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12 References

- Adams, S. V., Newcomb, P.A., 2014. Cadmium blood and urine concentrations as measures of exposure: NHANES 1999-2010. *J. Expo. Sci. Environ. Epidemiol.*
<https://doi.org/10.1038/jes.2013.55>
- Apel, P., Rousselle, C., Lange, R., Sissoko, F., Kolossa-Gehring, M., Ougier, E., 2020. Human biomonitoring initiative (HBM4EU) - Strategy to derive human biomonitoring guidance values (HBM-GVs) for health risk assessment. *Int. J. Hyg. Environ. Health* 230, 113622.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2020.113622>
- Berglund, M., Larsson, K., Grandér, M., Casteleyn, L., Kolossa-Gehring, M., Schwedler, G., Castaño, A., Esteban, M., Angerer, J., Koch, H.M., Schindler, B.K., Schoeters, G., Smolders, R., Exley, K., Sepai, O., Blumen, L., Horvat, M., Knudsen, L.E., Mørck, T.A., Joas, A., Joas, R., Biot, P., Aerts, D., De Cremer, K., Van Overmeire, I., Katsonouri, A., Hadjipanayis, A., Cerna, M., Krskova, A., Nielsen, J.K.S., Jensen, J.F., Rudnai, P., Kozepesy, S., Griffin, C., Nesbitt, I., Gutleb, A.C., Fischer, M.E., Ligocka, D., Jakubowski, M., Reis, M.F., Namorado, S., Lupsa, I.-R., Gurzau, A.E., Halzlova, K., Jajcaj, M., Mazej, D., Tratnik, J.S., Lopez, A., Cañas, A., Lehmann, A., Crettaz, P., Hond, E. Den, Govarts, E., 2015. Exposure determinants of cadmium in European mothers and their children. *Environ. Res.* 141, 69–76. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2014.09.042>
- Buekers, J., David, M., Koppen, G., Bessems, J., Scheringer, M., Lebret, E., Sarigiannis, D., Kolossa-Gehring, M., Berglund, M., Schoeters, G., Trier, X., 2018. Development of Policy Relevant Human Biomonitoring Indicators for Chemical Exposure in the European Population. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 15, 2085. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph15102085>
- Buekers, J., Morrens, B., Loots, I., Ganzleben, C., Schoeters, G., 2019. Inequalities in chemical exposure, in: *Environmental Health Inequalities in Europe: Second Assessment Report*. WHO, Regional Office for Europe, Copenhagen, WHO, pp. 84–89.
- Caporossi, L., Papaleo, B., 2015. Exposure to bisphenol A and gender differences: from rodents to humans evidences and hypothesis about the health effects. *J. Xenobiotics* 5, 5264.
<https://doi.org/10.4081/xeno.2015.5264>
- Covaci, A., Den Hond, E., Geens, T., Govarts, E., Koppen, G., Frederiksen, H., Knudsen, L.E., Mørck, T.A., Gutleb, A.C., Guignard, C., Cocco, E., Horvat, M., Heath, E., Kosjek, T., Mazej, D., Tratnik, J.S., Castaño, A., Esteban, M., Cutanda, F., Ramos, J.J., Berglund, M., Larsson, K., Jönsson, B.A.G., Biot, P., Casteleyn, L., Joas, R., Joas, A., Bloemen, L., Sepai, O., Exley, K., Schoeters, G., Angerer, J., Kolossa-Gehring, M., Fiddicke, U., Aerts, D., Koch, H.M., 2015. Urinary BPA measurements in children and mothers from six European member states: Overall results and determinants of exposure. *Environ. Res.* 141, 77–85. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2014.08.008>
- Den Hond, E., Govarts, E., Willems, H., Smolders, R., Casteleyn, L., Kolossa-Gehring, M., Schwedler, G., Seiwert, M., Fiddicke, U., Castaño, A., Esteban, M., Angerer, J., Koch, H.M., Schindler, B.K., Sepai, O., Exley, K., Bloemen, L., Horvat, M., Knudsen, L.E., Joas, A., Joas, R., Biot, P., Aerts, D., Koppen, G., Katsonouri, A., Hadjipanayis, A., Krskova, A., Maly, M., Mørck, T.A., Rudnai, P., Kozepesy, S., Mulcahy, M., Mannion, R., Gutleb, A.C., Fischer, M.E., Ligocka, D., Jakubowski, M., Reis, M.F., Namorado, S., Gurzau, A.E., Lupsa, I.-R., Halzlova, K., Jajcaj, M., Mazej, D., Tratnik, J.S., López, A., Lopez, E., Berglund, M., Larsson, K., Lehmann, A., Crettaz, P., Schoeters, G., 2015. First steps toward harmonized human biomonitoring in Europe: demonstration project to perform human biomonitoring on a European scale. *Environ. Health Perspect.* 123, 255–63. <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.1408616>

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EFSA, 2020. PFAS in food: EFSA assesses risk and sets tolerable intake [WWW Document]. URL <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/news/pfas-food-efsa-assesses-risks-and-sets-tolerable-intake>

EFSA, 2012. Cadmium dietary exposure in the European population. *EFSA J.* 10, 2551.

EFSA, 2009. Cadmium in Food: Scientific Opinion of the Panel on Contaminants in the Food Chain.

Koch, H.M., Rütther, M., Schütze, A., Conrad, A., Pälme, C., Apel, P., Brüning, T., Kolossa-Gehring, M., 2017. Phthalate metabolites in 24-h urine samples of the German Environmental Specimen Bank (ESB) from 1988 to 2015 and a comparison with US NHANES data from 1999 to 2012. *Int. J. Hyg. Environ. Health* 220, 130–141. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2016.11.003>

Pollock, T., Arbuckle, T.E., Guth, M., Bouchard, M.F., St-Amand, A., 2021. Associations among urinary triclosan and bisphenol A concentrations and serum sex steroid hormone measures in the Canadian and U.S. Populations. *Environ. Int.* 146, 106229. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2020.106229>

Smolders, R., Den Hond, E., Koppen, G., Govarts, E., Willems, H., Casteleyn, L., Kolossa-Gehring, M., Fiddicke, U., Castaño, A., Koch, H.M., Angerer, J., Esteban, M., Sepai, O., Exley, K., Bloemen, L., Horvat, M., Knudsen, L.E., Joas, A., Joas, R., Biot, P., Aerts, D., Katsonouri, A., Hadjipanayis, A., Cerna, M., Krskova, A., Schwedler, G., Seiwert, M., Nielsen, J.K.S., Rudnai, P., Közepesy, S., Evans, D.S., Ryan, M.P., Gutleb, A.C., Fischer, M.E., Ligocka, D., Jakubowski, M., Reis, M.F., Namorado, S., Lupsa, I.-R., Gurzau, A.E., Halzlova, K., Fabianova, E., Mazej, D., Tratnik Snoj, J., Gomez, S., González, S., Berglund, M., Larsson, K., Lehmann, A., Crettaz, P., Schoeters, G., 2015. Interpreting biomarker data from the COPHES/DEMOCOPHES twin projects: Using external exposure data to understand biomarker differences among countries. *Environ. Res.* 141, 86–95. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2014.08.016>

Takeuchi, T., Tsutsumi, O., 2002. Serum bisphenol a concentrations showed gender differences, possibly linked to androgen levels. *Biochem. Biophys. Res. Commun.* 291, 76–78. <https://doi.org/10.1006/bbrc.2002.6407>

Vacchi-Suzzi, C., Eriksen, K.T., Levine, K., McElroy, J., Tjønneland, A., Raaschou-Nielsen, O., Harrington, J.M., Meliker, J.R., 2015. Dietary Intake Estimates and Urinary Cadmium Levels in Danish Postmenopausal Women. *PLoS One* 10, e0138784. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0138784>

WHO, 2015. Human biomonitoring: facts and figures.

13 Annex 1: Overview of indicators to be derived

Table 11: Overview of indicators that will be derived under Task 5.4. Statistical analysis is done by WP10 on Data Management and Analysis before the data is used

Indicator	Parameter	Calculation	Interpretation
Temporal increase or stabilisation of internal exposure possibly related to policy action	Temporal trends of substance (P50 values measured throughout the relevant time period, including first P50 value and the last measured P50 value) related to policy actions/implementation.	<p>Increase in substance concentration:</p> $x\% = \left(\frac{\text{Last P50value} - \text{firstP50value}}{\text{first P50 value}} \right) \times 100$	Increase in substance concentration or stable concentration may indicate an emerging chemical or it may indicate that policy actions taken are not effective or not effective enough to cause a (further) decrease.
Possible effectiveness of policy actions in minimising chemical exposure Eg. Efficiency indicators (Type C): Are we improving? Policy effectiveness indicators (Type D): Are the measures working?	Temporal trends of substance (P50 values measured throughout the relevant time period, including first P50 value and the last measured P50 value in whole time period needed with an absolute minimum of 3 values in the temporal trend) possibly related to policy actions/implementation	<p>Decrease of substance concentration:</p> $x\% = \left(\frac{\text{First P50value} - \text{LastP50value}}{\text{firstP50value}} \right) \times 100$	Decrease of substance concentration possibly related with efficient policy actions.

Indicator	Parameter	Calculation	Interpretation
Inequality of internal chemical exposure	Stratification for different age groups (P50 values used for time trends)	No overlap of 95% confidence interval on mean internal exposure values of different age groups is considered as “differences in exposure”. In future, when high quality data sets will become available through the HBM4EU aligned studies, in-depth statistical testing for significant differences will be performed to find additional differences than those just based on ‘non-overlap’ of 95% confidence intervals of two subpopulations like age groups.	Differences in internal exposure between different age groups exist.
			No indication of differences in exposure between different age groups.
	Stratification for sex (women/men) (P50 values used for time trends)	No overlap of 95% confidence interval between mean internal exposure values of different sexes is considered as “differences in exposures”.	Women are more highly exposed than men.
			Men are more highly exposed than women.
			No indication of sex differences.
	Stratification for ISCED (P50 values used for time trends)	ISCED related “differences in chemical burden of exposure” are based on no overlap of 95% confidence interval.	People with different educational level (based on ISCED) do differ in chemical exposure (educational level is used as a proxy for differences in life style and environment).
			No direct/strong indication for correlation between educational level and chemical exposure.
	Stratification for countries (P50 values used for time trends)	Statistical significance of country differences in chemical burden of exposure. Link with one of WP10’s outcomes on distributions of exposure in different countries. This is only valid when the country’s data are representative for the country.	Differences in internal exposure between countries indicated.
			Differences in burden of exposure between countries appear absent.

Indicator	Parameter	Calculation	Interpretation
Health relevance regarding internal chemical exposure	Extent of exceedance: 95 th Percentile in relation to human biomonitoring guidance values (HBM-GV)	$E_{exceedance} = \frac{P_{95}}{HBM\ GV}$	<p>Value > 1: Indicates how far the 95th percentile is above the health-based guidance values. The higher the value above 1, the larger the probability of health impact based on current knowledge.</p> <p>Results can be used in priority setting framework to rank substances for further actions.</p>
	Percentage of exceedance: Individual data of n (number of participants exceeding HBM-GV) and N (total number of participants) for each country	$P_{exceedance} = \frac{(n > HBM - GV)}{N} \times 100\%$	<p>Value < 1: I.e. $E_{exceedance} < 1$. At least 95% of sampled population shows internal exposures below HBM-GV.</p> <p>P > 0 %. A proportional number of participants exceed the HBM-GV. Risk of health impairment for that part of the population cannot be excluded.</p> <p>Results can be used in priority setting framework to rank substances for further actions.</p> <p>P = 0 %. No participants exceed the HBM-GV. There is no anticipated risk of health impairment according to current knowledge.</p>

The indicators task will use the aggregated data that has been revised under WP10.

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